

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Mengno**FIRST NAME:** Fonyuy Francis**PROGRAM CODE:** DCCS**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** DR. GULMA**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Writing a good academic essay (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 5-13)
3. Some rule of thumb for writing papers (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 1-4)
4. Referencing in an academic essay (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 11)

WRITING AN EXCELLENT ACADEMIC PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing an academic paper has always been my main issue. This is because when I see a huge dissertation with so many pages, I ponder the type of style, language, and format that is being used to have an excellent book ready for defense to earn academic titles. These days, since I started my Ph.D. program with Euclid University online, I have been familiarizing myself with these questions by reading through the documents and watching the course video on writing a response paper. Although I am from an English-speaking country, I have always been eager for perfection, especially when writing academic papers and dissertations. Reading this period one material and watching the video has made me become fully aware that the English language is a continuous learning process that leads to perfection and thus made me realize I have a lot to do to perfect my English competency.

However, after reading the revised version, of course, ACA-401D by Prof. Laurent Cleenwerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma and watching the basic tutorials by Prof. Cleenwerck on language, citation style, and how to use paragraphs, headings when writing a response paper, I discovered that learning is a continuous process. If one needs a good essay, he/she needs to understand the basics and forms of writing, such as referencing, citations, punctuation, and good sentence construction with the right spellings; the use of English

should be properly decided to avoid the mix of British and US English and others just to name a few are very important.

My response paper will be limited to seven important major perceptions from the course material that I have studied from the ACA-401D course material for period one and the basic tutorial videos that will include writing a good academic essay, use of English style (British vs. American), rules of thumb, style guide, referencing and citation, tables, common Latin abbreviations used in writing, and plagiarism.

2) WRITING ACADEMIC ESSAY

The first chapter of the course material deliberates on the essentials of essay writing. It expatiated on how to develop and write a good essay, starting from the preparation needed in easy writing, introduction and how to construct the paragraph and ensure the flow of information and ideas (coherent), the tips on essay writing, body, and conclusion.

According to the revised version of ACA-401D by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, there are many types of essays. Scholarly writing is non-fictional writing produced as part of academic work (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 1). Examples of academic writing include research findings or reports on empirical fieldwork which may not or may be published in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals (or remain as manuscripts, theses, or dissertations); monographs; conference papers; book or literature review; explication; technical report; translation; students' presentations; as well as undergraduate versions.

An academic essay has the objective of answering a question or a task; to ensure its effectiveness, it needs to be backed by evidence. To achieve this, one must prepare consequently by undertaking thorough research about the subjects they are writing about (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 2). Developing a plan, determining the approach to the task, and setting time to conduct adequate research to achieve a good essay is essential for a good academic essay. I am in support of this idea because if we look at the research world, we discover that many research works in the academic world help to support the pre-existing hypothesis that needs more deepening to clarify sections that were not touched by other research topics on the same subjects. It is, therefore, important for one to take key notes while researching to ensure that a keynote of useful information on other research papers is presented in the literature review and should be referenced.

It should be well noted that no matter what the type of essay is, there is always a structure to follow. The essay should be structured so as to communicate their ideas clearly and answer the questions objectively. For most papers, particularly those at EUCLID, the accepted structure should be an introduction, body, and conclusion (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 3). The structure is like building blocks of the house that make the academic essay look organised and easily communicated in an orderly style. It makes the work look coherent, promotes uniformity, and makes the review by instructors easier.

The steps for writing are not rigidly linear. Still, the basic steps in writing an essay according to the pyramid of essay writing are Analysing the question and defining the key terms, establishing the points of review, researching the topic by using credible academic sources, taking notes from your preliminary reading, developing your essay plan and organize your idea, draft your essay into main parts (introduction, body, and conclusion), keep the draft aside for 1-2 days then review it and make changes if any, edit and redraft the essay, have a colleague or friend read it, complete or check your reference and hand in the essay (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 3).

The period one-course pack and the videos have given me an insight into what I should take into consideration when planning to write a good academic paper. This course has actually addressed many doubts I was nurturing and has set me ready for better production of academic works.

3) RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

It is important to note that when writing an academic paper, it is good to personalize the essay by giving your line of thoughts and arguments that are evidence-based. When criticizing another person's work, even when having divergent thoughts, the writing should be respectful with empathy (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 14). As a writer, before you present a divergent thought, ensure there is evidence to support your critics or discredit them.

In embarking on a journey of essay writing, one should endeavor to ensure that the main thesis idea is stated from the beginning, preferably in the opening paragraph, to set the pace of the work. The writer should stay focused by ensuring that your papers critically assess some important aspects of the theories discussed in this course material by respecting the aspect that before getting to the evaluation, you will need relevant aspects of your assessments and guiding your presentation to particular problems that animate your paper (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 13). Do not lead with such sweeping generalities and write clearly by writing short sentences, avoiding page-long paragraphs, being careful to signal transitions and ensuring that your attention is focused on the idea you wish to express. Avoid your writing from being boring and clumsy by introducing some stylistic variety and shy away from long strings of prepositional clauses.

I will support the fact that a writer should ensure that their essay is interesting so that the reader can be kept motivated and have the zeal to read more by making interesting and catchy introductions. When writing, assertions should be backed with evidence and not left hanging. This makes your paper to be credible. Once assertions are supported, credit should also be given to those sources so that plagiarism is avoided, for it is an academic offense that needs to be avoided at all costs.

Continuous studying of this course material is very important for the realization of a standard academic paper. Thus, one must dedicate time to reading, re-reading, and editing his/her work, and where support is needed, one should seek it from others who are deemed to be helpful, like the lecturers (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 16).

4) PLAGIARISM

According to Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021, 34), when writing a paper, one of the most important things the writer should do is avoid plagiarism. Plagiarism is “using a source of information without giving credit to the author of the information.” Many definitions of plagiarism exist, but since we are at Euclid University, our focus will be on the definition given by the institution. It is important to always acknowledge the source of information; failure to adhere has academic repercussions. Ethically, in academics, plagiarism is wrong and unethical (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 5). Using someone’s work and refusing to acknowledge it is only disrespectful and incompetent. They should not expect their work to be given academic rights or authorship. Thus, all writers should always desist from using someone's work without acknowledgment.

The key point to be noted is that writers should always give credit to the source of their information when using any quote, paraphrase, statistical data, or visual (such as a graph) that is borrowed from another source. To avoid this, the solution is to use proper citations and references of authors and their sources that have provided the information one is using (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 6).

5) REFERENCING

It is important to note that all academic essays **MUST** contain references. Only references guard against plagiarism, which is a serious academic offense (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 11). Because of this, it is important to inquire and understand the referencing style of each faculty, school, or journal. Some will provide guidance on the referencing standard they prefer.

Nevertheless, some schools, such as EUCLID, will accept any form of referencing if the user is consistent throughout his/her work. All students should ensure to reference their work properly and should be consistent, for it helps to give clarity and uniformity throughout your research work.

My take-home message after completing the section of the study material is that all work should be properly cited and referenced to avoid the pit of plagiarism, which is an academic offense.

6) CONCLUSION

In this module of the course materials, I have enriched myself with the various academic writing precautions to be taken during my response papers and academic work. This session is an introductory course for my Ph.D. program in Climate Change and Sustainability, which has been an academic traffic light orientation and warning for me to

set the pace for my achievements. It has been a very enriching experience to read the course material and orientation documents, and videos.

This section has made me realize that more effort needs to be put in to succeed in this journey of academic titles by respecting and acknowledging other people's work, using proper citation and referencing consistently, respecting the rules of thumb during academic writing, and being coherent on the writing style and language in an orderly manner to keep the work interesting and reader-friendly by not using jargons and complicated words and sentences.

REFERENCES

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